

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Environmental costs of the use of green manure in wheat cultivation in Flanders (Belgium)

Green manure is a sustainable alternative to chemical fertilizers as it improves soil health and reduces environmental impact. The aim of this study is to determine how different types of green manure affect the environmental costs associated with wheat production. The analysis of environmental costs (€ per € gross margin for the farmer) helps to identify practices that reduce impacts without compromising agricultural profitability and provides valuable information for policy makers promoting sustainable agricultural practices.

An environmental cost-benefit analysis (e-CBA) based on life cycle assessment (LCA) was applied to compare four fertilization strategies: (T1) cattle manure, (T2) vermicompost, (T3) ensiled grass, and (T4) control without organic fertilization.

The results show that livestock manure is the fertilization practice that best combines sustainability and profitability, as it has the lowest environmental cost (0.06 €/€), which is 5% lower than the control treatment. In this case, only the impacts generated in the field are considered, as the impacts associated with the handling and storage of manure are attributed to livestock farming rather than crop production. Secondly, the use of worm compost has a similar environmental impact as the control treatment (only 2% higher), while the cost of grass silage is 31% higher than the cost of not using green manure (control treatment). In the latter case, the impacts related to processing, transportation and silage emissions could explain the higher costs despite the benefits for soil health.

1. Environmental costs (€ impact per € gross margin for the farmer) for each practice tested.

KEYWORDS

Environmental costs, impacts, wheat production, green manure, organic farming

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